

ENHANCING RETENTION OF BIOLOGY CONCEPT THROUGH VISUAL-BASED PEDAGOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11629594>

ABSTRACT

This action research focuses on enhancing learner retention in biology through visual-based pedagogy, particularly focusing on Grade 10 students at Musuan Integrated School (MIS) during the 2023-2024 school year. The rationale stems from the uncertainties post-pandemic and the need for improved teaching methodologies in biological education. The study aligns with Philippine Education Program goals and research insights emphasizing contextualized instructional materials and the efficacy of visuals in promoting learning. The research utilized a Two-shot Post-test design with mixed methods, integrating quantitative data from a 40-item multiple-choice test and qualitative data from semi-structured interviews. The study aimed to assess if significant differences existed in pre-test and post-test scores after implementing visual-based pedagogy. Results revealed a substantive increase in post-intervention assessment scores, indicating statistically significant improvements in conceptual mastery and retention. Students' perceptions highlighted the positive impact of visual-based pedagogy on learning environments, collaborative learning, and effective outcomes. These findings underscore the efficacy of visual aids and interactive activities in fostering deep comprehension and knowledge retention, aligning with previous research findings. Recommendations include incorporating visual-based pedagogy and technology with diverse visuals such flowcharts, diagrams, pictures, computer simulations, video presentations. This can lead to fostering positive learning environments, emphasizing

hands-on activities, and continuous support for sustained effectiveness. Further research and professional development are encouraged to explore and implement innovative strategies in visual-based instruction for enhanced learning outcomes.

Keywords: *Visual-Based Pedagogy, Retention, Perception, Pre-Test, Immediate Post-Test, Delayed Post.*

INTRODUCTION

The pandemic profound modification and the current status of the learners in this post-pandemic setting are currently indefinite and do not show the right succession of clear improvement of the teaching-learning process especially in the field of biological education and its multidisciplinary concept. Biology is the most visually appealing of all sciences. However, many teaching aids can be employed extensively in the teaching of biology to bring the subject to life in the students' minds by developing animated mental images (T. Demissie et al., 2016). The Philippine Education Program has strengthened academic foundations with local and accessible resources, aligning with the RA 10533 (Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2016) requirements for a contextualized and global curriculum. In the insights of (LPT, 2020) & (Garin et al. 2017). Utilizing contextualized instructional materials unlocks students' maximum learning potential, leading to improved academic performance. Furthermore, poor teaching strategies and inadequate resources result in less engagement in lessons and using visual aids, audio-visual tools, and tangible materials enhances students' understanding capabilities, leading to impressive learning outcomes (Rivera & Sanchez, 2020) and (Kaminski & Sloutsky, 2020).

According to Cuban (2014), it suggests that 83% of what we learn is through sight, making it a dominant factor. Additionally, people tend to remember 30% of what they see, emphasizing the effectiveness of visuals. Therefore, it is morally right to engage students in the teaching and learning process by stimulating them or keeping them engaged. Moreover, Visual Based Pedagogy can be a number of different types of educational resources that be also views as beneficial instructional and learning visual aids, including like motion pictures, video games, television shows, and synchronized audio-slide projectors, PCs, computer-assisted instructions, and more equipment that multimedia promotes quicker communication in foreign languages (Ahmad, 2016). However, the majority of educators in Musuan Integrated School (MIS) use less sufficient visual aids as part of their teaching strategies. This has a direct impact on learning outcomes and could create obstacles for the teaching and learning process.

In the study of Adebisi et al. (2021). It's highlighted that the idea of utilizing science learning materials to teach biology concepts has a notable impact on enhancing students' ability to retain information and ultimately boosts the academic performance of senior high school students. According to Jamal Raiyn (2016), visual-based pedagogy represents an impactful classroom learning strategy that places a strong emphasis on conveying information through visual mediums, including images, diagrams, flowcharts, and

interactive simulations. The teacher's role involves overseeing the learning process and determining the most effective means to enhance higher-order thinking (HOT) skills. Employing this approach can significantly aid students in memorizing key biological concepts and comprehending complex biological processes (Sumarmin R., 2018).

Analyzing the differences in retention results achieved through visual-based pedagogy can be instrumental in shaping action plans and fostering educational innovation. By comparing the performance of students with higher and lower retention rates, educators can pinpoint effective strategies used by high-retention students and share these practices more widely. Furthermore, Shabiralyani et al. (2015) emphasize that visual aids play a crucial role in encouraging students during the learning process, ensuring better understanding of lessons, generating interest in the subject matter, aiding in the permanent retention of learned materials, enhancing students' vocabulary, and providing direct experiences for the students.

The results of this research have value for learners, teachers, and school administrators as they shed light on the crucial role of the learning environment in nurturing students' knowledge and skills. The purpose of this study is to enhance the retention of biology concepts through visual-based pedagogy. Identify if there is a significant difference in the 1st and 2nd post-test scores of students following the implementation.

Research Questions

The study investigated the effects of using Visual-Based Pedagogy on Enhancing Retention of Biology Concept on the Grade 10 learners of Musuan Integrated School, in the third quarter of the School Year 2023-2024.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of students' retention of biology concepts when expose to Visual-Based Pedagogy in terms of:
 - a. Pre-test?
 - b. Immediate Post-test?
 - c. Delayed Post-test?
2. Is there a significant difference on students' retention in Biology when exposed to Visual-Based Pedagogy in terms of:
 - a. Pre-test compared to Immediate post-test scores.
 - b. Pre-test compared to Delayed post-test scores.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a Two-shot Post-test design to gauge the participants' retention of the subject matter. Before the intervention, a pre-test was administered, followed by a post-test. After that, a second shot post-test was administered after a two-week interval.

A. Participants and/or Other Sources of Information and Data

Research Design

The study employed a mixed method research design utilizing both quantitative and qualitative data gathering procedures. This study utilized a Two-shot post-test and focused on the systematic collection, analysis, and interpretation of numerical data to address research questions or test hypotheses. Meanwhile, qualitative data on the perceptions of learners with the use of this approach was also explored. It utilizes thematic analysis where themes and core ideas were sought from a semi-structured interview questionnaire given to the learners.

In gathering information, the researchers utilized forty (40) item multiple choice tests focusing on the concept of biology specifically the Endocrine System for Grade 10 students during the first semester of the school year 2023-2024.

Locale of the Study

Figure 1. Map of MIS, showing the research locale.

The Community-Based Action Research (CBAR) that was conducted took place at Musuan Integrated School (MIS), located in Musuan, Maramag, Bukidnon, Philippines. MIS administered a comprehensive educational program, encompassing kindergarten through junior high school, and operated under the auspices of the Department of Education. Renowned for its exemplary track record in both academic and non-academic pursuits, MIS stood as a beacon of educational excellence in the region.

Participants of the Study

The participants of the study were the Grade 10 students under the Enhanced K–12 Basic Education Curriculum of Musuan Integrated School (MIS) for the school year 2023–2024. The researchers only chose the subtopics of Endocrine System prior to focusing on biology concepts in the implementation of a visual-based pedagogy intervention. The study only covered the final term of the second semester.

Instrumentation

The researcher designed and constructed a forty (40) item multiple-choice test to measure the level of retention of the learners. A two-way table of specification (TOS) was prepared prior to the making of the test items. The test was subjected to content validation by an expert in biology to determine if the constructed test items would be appropriate to test the learners' retention.

The retention of students in statistics and probability was analyzed and interpreted using the table below. The DepEd Order No.8 series of 2015 grading scale with the corresponding descriptor was modified in interpreting the retention level of the students.

<u>Percent Scale</u>	<u>Descriptive Rating</u>	<u>Qualitative Description</u>
90%-100%	Outstanding	Very High Retention
85%-89%	Very Satisfying	High Retention
80%-84%	Satisfying	Moderate
75%-79%	Fairly Satisfying	Low Retention
Below 75%	Did Not Meet Expectation	Very Low Retention

B. Data Gathering Methods

The following steps were taken to gather the needed data from identified participants: (1) Approval was sought from IERC for the conduct of the study. (2) Permission was obtained from the school head in order to conduct the action research. (3) Then the researchers oriented the students on how the visual-based pedagogy would be implemented.

Before implementing the intervention, a pre-test was administered to the intact Grade 10 students. Subsequently, a visual-based pedagogy intervention was employed to enhance retention of complex biology concepts. Following the intervention, the students underwent a post-test after a two-week interval the delayed post-test then followed.

A semi-structured interview questionnaire was also given to the learners to determine their perception on the use of visual based pedagogy.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were employed to assess the level of retention among learners both before and after the intervention. To ascertain if a significant difference existed in the retention of learners before and after the intervention, a paired t-test was utilized.

(Ping & Renandya, 2020) explain that the t-test is utilized to compare two sets of scores, determining whether the average score (referred to as the mean score) of the first set differs significantly from that of the second set. Descriptive statistics is used in this research because it best describes and summarizes the data by providing an overview of the important characteristics of the sample (George, 2023).

For the qualitative data, a thematic analysis from the students' responses was utilized to determine the student's perception on the use of Visual Based Pedagogy in Biology instruction.

RESULTS

This section presented the analysis and interpretation from the data gathered in determining the retention of the students using the visual-based pedagogy on the Grade 10 learners of Musuan Integrated School for the School Year 2023-2024. The groups of data presented in this section were based on the order of action research questions posed in this study.

For Quantitative Result:

Level of Student's Retention Before and After the Intervention

Table 1 presents the students' prior knowledge and retention before and after the intervention.

Table 1. Students Retention Before and After the Intervention.

Percent Scale	Pre-Test		Immediate post-test		Delayed post-test		Qualitative Description
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
90%-100%	0	0	1	2	2	3	Very High Retention
85%-89%	0	0	1	2	7	1 2	High Retention
80%-84%	0	0	8	13	12	2 0	Moderate
75%-79%	0	0	16	27	10	1 7	Low Retention
74%- Below	60	100	34	57	29	4 8	Very Low Retention
Mean	11.97		27.65		29.07		
SD	3.46		4.26		4.36		

Difference on Learner's pre-test, Immediate Post-test and Delayed Post-test

Table 2. Difference of the Learners pre-test, Immediate Post-test and Delayed post-test.

Pair	Mean	SD	t	Sig (2-tailed)
pre-test- Immediate Post- Test	-15.68	5.31	-22.88	.000
pre-test- Delayed Post-Test	-17.10	5.33	-24.86	.000

*Significant at $P < 0.05$

Difference on Learner's Immediate Post-test and Delayed Post-test

Table 3. Presents the difference of Immediate Post-test and Delayed Post-test.

Pair	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig (2-tailed)
post-test_1 -post-test_2	-1.41667	1.63947	-6.693	59	.000

Significant at P < 0.05

For Qualitative Result:

Student's perception on the Use of Visual Based Pedagogy

Table 4. Major Themes and Core Ideas of the Student's Perception on the Use of Visual Based Pedagogy.

Major Themes	Sub Theme	Core Ideas
Effective Learning Outcome	Positive Learning Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning is fun and interesting • Group collaboration
	Improve Retention Level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better understanding through Contextualize content • Lessons made easier to remember

DISCUSSION

Quantitative Discussion

As shown in table 1, all of the student's pre-test score was below 74% indicating a qualitative interpretation of Very Low Retention with an overall mean score of 11.97 (SD=3.469). This might be attributed to student's little information and less prior knowledge on the lessons before receiving a formal instruction using the strategic Visual Based Pedagogy. This result conforms to the report of Guskey and McTighe (2016), that pre-assessment is teachers' way of determining students' prior knowledge before the instruction is given.

The tabulated data presents compelling evidence of a substantive upsurge in

learners' post-intervention assessment scores. Notably, a mean score of 27.65 (SD=4.26) indicates a statistically significant enhancement in conceptual mastery following the implementation of visual-based pedagogy. Furthermore, the persistence of elevated scores in the delayed post-test, averaging at 29.07 (SD=4.36) even after a two-week interval, underscores the durability of the observed learning gains. These findings resonate with the efficacy of visual-based instructional strategies in fostering deep comprehension and knowledge retention. The outcomes not only underscore the immediate impact of the intervention but also provide empirical validation for its sustained effectiveness in promoting enduring conceptual understanding among learners.

The study's outcomes suggest that utilizing visual-based teaching methods is highly effective in improving information retention, especially for understanding complex biology topics. The comparison between immediate and delayed post-test scores highlights a notable improvement, indicating a high level of retention among students following the intervention. These findings are in line with research by Vanichvasin P (2021), which revealed that students exposed to visual-based learning demonstrate enhanced attention spans, comprehension abilities, and retention skills. Two weeks following the immediate post-test, a delayed post-test was administered, yielding positive results. Additionally, visual-based approaches contribute to memory enhancement by aiding in the recall, retention, and retrieval of course material. It's worth noting that such methods also stimulate greater student motivation, interest, and satisfaction, ultimately resulting in improved memorization and overall academic performance.

As reflected in the table 2, the negative mean difference indicated that the mean score of learners is higher in the post-test compared to the pre-test scores of learners. This means that the use of visual based strategies has been beneficial to the learners. In addition, it can be noted that the difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of learners resulted in a p-value of 0.000 which is significant at $p < 0.05$. The result shows that there is a significant difference in the scores of the learners before and after the intervention is employed so therefore the null hypothesis is rejected.

This result is congruent to the study of Pem K (2019) states those engaged in visual-based learning methods show significant advancements in higher-order cognitive abilities, critical thinking prowess, and retention of knowledge especially in the field of biology.

As reflected in the table 3, the negative mean difference indicates that the mean scores of the Delayed Post-test compared to the immediate post-test are higher. This indicates that the students have retained the information in the given 40 item test.

In addition, it can be noted that the difference between the immediate post-test scores and the delayed post-test scores have resulted in a p value of 0.000 which is significant at $p < 0.05$. This means that there is a significant difference between the scores of the learners after a two-week interval.

This result can be due to the fact that the researchers did not alter a change in the

test questionnaire in the delayed post-test which contributed to the student's retention rate. In Federer's (2014) study, an intriguing finding emerged in which the familiarity of questions, especially those enriched with visual elements, significantly shaped students' responses. This implies that the order of questions might not wield as much influence on scores as factors like question familiarity and the presence of visual aids do. Consequently, the study's outcomes shed light on the efficacy of visual-based pedagogy in student learning. The observed improvement in students' overall scores across pre-test, immediate post-test, and delayed post-test underscores the profound impact of such interventions.

Qualitative Discussion

Positive Learning Environment

Visual-based pedagogy made the lesson captivating for learners. It also encouraged active participation in discussions, especially given the visually appealing nature of the endocrine system topic. Students found video simulations in the discussion to be both motivating and effective. Additionally, they enjoyed engaging in hands-on activities such as "Label me, complete me," which served to assess their prior knowledge. An unlabeled illustration of the endocrine system was provided for identification purposes. Furthermore, a group activity involved creating posters depicting potential problems resulting from endocrine system dysfunction, which were then presented to the class.

The researcher's interest was piqued by the participants' responses in the questionnaire. Their answers indicated that the activities made the subject interesting and not boring. Similarly, another student recalled, *"As a student, the experience of identifying and labeling the anatomy of the endocrine system and its functions was enjoyable. Our biology class is fun because of group activities where we can share knowledge with each other."*

This result is similar to the findings of Bulunuz (2011) who revealed that student's involvement through activities were found exciting, fun and interesting and that students who found the lessons fun and interesting are highly motivated as it creates a positive learning environment thus enhances their participation and engagement of learners in the class (Fallon, Walsh and Prendergast, 2013). This agrees with the work of Gillani (2009) who discovered that when instructional technology is applied as a supplementary approach in teaching of Biology; the students of the experimental group were more attentive because the use of instructional technology stimulated interest and enhanced the motivational level of students. Therefore, the students found learning enjoyable as they collaborated with their peers or group mates, fostering engagement and active participation in group activities. This collaborative approach likely enhanced their understanding of the material through shared insights and perspectives, contributing to a more comprehensive learning experience.

Improve Retention Level

An integral discovery from this study underscores the effectiveness of employing visual-based pedagogy as an intervention in the learning process. Utilizing modern visual aids and leveraging technology to deliver instructional materials not only encourages active student participation but also significantly enhances retention of key concepts. Visual stimuli have been shown to capture students' attention more effectively than traditional teaching methods, leading to increased retention of key concepts. Additionally, the use of visuals can help make complex information more understandable and memorable for students. Overall, incorporating visual-based pedagogy can greatly enhance the learning experience and improve students' ability to grasp and retain important information.

This concept is related to the statement of three students who similarly cited that, *“By implementing visual based pedagogy, there are many lessons that I figured out clearly”*. *“The activities conducted in this subject helped me a lot in my studies, because it helped me understand the topics very well”*. *“Nakatabang jud siya, kay masabtan man og maayo ang mga functions sa kada organs responsible for secreting hormones especially kay naay pictures and video presentations”*.

This agrees with the work of Shabiralyani et al. (2015) emphasizes that visual based play a crucial role in encouraging students during the learning process, ensuring better understanding of lessons, generating interest in the subject matter, aiding in the higher retention of learned materials, enhancing students' vocabulary, and providing direct experiences for the students. Additionally, Cope (2014) stated that active participation during instruction increases learning and retention. Students learn more efficiently by participating in instruction. To further support this idea, Iji, (2002) and Chianson (2014), stated that retention in biology is not acquired by mere rote learning but through appropriate instructional delivery approach. In conclusion, utilizing visual-based pedagogy with the integration of visual aids such as videos, images, diagrams, and interactive multimedia presentations to convey information and concepts to students. When combined with technology, such as interactive whiteboards, educational software, and online resources, these visual tools can offer dynamic significant benefits in terms of student learning and retention.

Conclusions

Based on the gathered results from the study, the researchers concluded the following:

The results highlight the effectiveness of visual-based pedagogy in improving students' retention. The findings support the use of visual aids and interactive activities to enhance learning outcomes. Students' positive perception of the approach underscores the importance of creating an engaging learning environment. The study aligns with previous research, emphasizing the benefits of visual-based learning in attention span, comprehension, retention, and memory.

Recommendations

Based on the results and discussion, the following recommendations are made:

1. Educators should incorporate visual-based pedagogy by using visual aids like charts, diagrams, simulation, and video presentation to enhance learning outcomes.
2. Creating a positive learning environment through collaboration and interactive discussions can further enhance students' engagement and participation.
3. Emphasize the use of hands-on activities to facilitate better understanding and retention of the content.
4. Provide continuous support and reinforcement to sustain the effectiveness of visual-based pedagogy.
5. Further research and professional development should be pursued to explore more effective strategies and stay updated with advancements in visual-based instruction.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

1. We, CHRISCENTE JOSE CABUNGCAL, CARLA MARIE CAPUYAN, MA. THERESA ISABEL DECHOSA, DARAH FAYE SABIO, CATHERINE SALDUA, the researchers of the study entitled **“ENHANCING RETENTION OF BIOLOGY CONCEPT THROUGH VISUAL-BASED PEDAGOGY”**. This form is part of a process called “informed consent” to allow you to understand this study before deciding whether or not to take part. This study is being conducted by the researchers in Musuan Integrated School, Musuan, Maramag, Bukidnon. Any information you provide will be kept anonymous. The researchers will not use your personal information for any purposes outside of this research study. Also, the researchers will not include your name or anything that could identify you in the study reports. Pieces of information provided by the participants will be treated with utmost care and held confidentiality.
2. The participation of the participants is completely voluntary and may withdraw from the study at any time. The study is completely anonymous; therefore, it does not require them to provide their name or any other identity information. Furthermore, the research data will be collected is ensured to be for academic purposes only and will remain confidential.
3. We hereby declare that we do not have any personal conflict of interest that may arise from our application and submission of our research proposal. We understand that our research proposal may be returned to us if found out that there is conflict of interest during the initial screening as per (insert RMG provision). Further, in case any form of conflict of interest (possible or actual) which may inadvertently emerge during the conduct of our research, we will duly report it to the research committee for immediate action. We understand that we may be held accountable by the Department of Education and (insert grant mechanism) for any conflict of interest which we have intentionally concealed.

4. Plagiarism was strictly avoided by ensuring that all sources and references were properly cited and original contributions were clearly distinguished. Furthermore, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings. The data was analyzed impartially, and conclusions were drawn based solely on the evidence collected. Finally, the results of the study were used purely for research purposes, contributing to the academic and scientific understanding of the subject matter, with no intention for commercial exploitation.

Acknowledgments

First and foremost, the researchers would want to express their gratitude to the Almighty God for providing them with the resources, wisdom, and favors necessary to carry out the research effectively. The following people have also helped the researchers out, and they would like to express their sincere gratitude to them:

Ms. Raihana Toke, whose encouragement, advice, and insights significantly improved our action research paper.

Ms. Garin Boiser, our friendly and approachable research adviser, for sharing valuable ideas and suggestions that enhanced the study's significance. We also express ongoing appreciation for her interest in the subject, feedback, and encouragement.

Mr. Milbert B. Bernel, for his expertise in proofreading and reviewing the research data and Cristila Marie Ibonia for helping in statistical analysis and running the data.

Grade 10 students of Musuan Integrated School, for their active cooperation and participation during the conduct of the study.

Researchers' family, for their unwavering love, support, and financial assistance, serving as our greatest sources of inspiration and motivation.

Block mates and friends, who faced similar challenges during the research process, and were always there to lend a helping hand and uplift each other.

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